

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**POLIO SUPPRESSION IS AFFECTED BY ELECTRONIC
MEDIA IN GENERAL PUBLIC IN THE URBAN AND RURAL
AREAS OF PAKISTAN**¹Dr. Ahssan ul-Haq, ²Dr. Mustansar Mansoor Gill, ³Dr. Sohaib Yousaf¹Medical Officer THQ Pattoki²The University of Lahore.³Medical Officer THQ Hospital Pattoki**Abstract:**

Objective: The most important objective is to find the person of electronic broadcasting to established polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0) in families which is related to any religion in our community. The target is that to link polio injection in families, which shows electronic broadcasting television and transistor with families which are not known about contact to electronic broadcasting.

Methodology: Pakistan demographic and well-being study is third national review, information which is collected is recycled for the survey. Survey held at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (January – November 2017). In this study, fourteen thousand families are chosen (six thousand nine hundred and forty-four in city regions and seven thousand and fifty-six from country regions). In addition, there are twelve thousand nine hundred and forty-three engaged families, which is engaged, families. Thirteen thousand five hundred and fifty-eight forever-marital females or three thousand one hundred and thirty-four forever-marital males which oldness in between in (15 – 49) are cross-examined. SPSS multinomial logistic relapse examined is analyzed to show the importance for the inquiry to connect under electronic board casting (television and transistor) with polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0). In addition, polio significance is <0.05 shows that statistically important.

Results: TV shows extra significance than the transistor in polio injection, kids of these families which has a television and transistor have more idea about the polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0) from those kid's families which do not have a television and transistor. Those families which having TV have more important advanced polio injected kids, injections period on cards and injection informed by parents from those which do not have a television in now a day.

Small regions of the nation in which families do not have a television and transistors in homes having more in numbers of polio unvaccinated kids as compared to the kids of the city. In Balochistan small regions families without transistor have 37.7% to 76.3% or without television has 37.3% to 80.5% polio unvaccinated (1, 2, 3, 0) kids its shows the large numbers of polio unvaccinated kids in the nation. Transistor and television are statistically important which is linked through polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0).

Conclusion: Electronic board casting television and transistor show his significance in polio injection which is showing an energetic part in polio suppression in Pakistan. Correct scheming or conceiving of control broadcasting note at a correct time is formed responsiveness around polio, variation performance to approach of polio injection.

Keywords: Poliomyelitis, injection, electronic board casting, nation.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Ahssan ul-Haq,**

Medical Officer THQ Pattoki

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ahssan ul-Haq et al., *Polio Suppression Is Affected By Electronic Media in General Public in the Urban and Rural Areas of Pakistan.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(10).

INTRODUCTION:

Poliomyelitis is a disease which is caused by a virus which is largely caused disease in the kids in age between 5 year-olds. The virus which caused poliomyelitis in kids it is diffused over a faecal-oral path or oral discharge. When poliovirus enters in the central nervous system it's causing a disease which leads to paralysis. Inappropriately here is no method for the prevented of poliovirus. It is just treated by injection or inoculation. If people are not inoculated or vaccinated the protected organization taken more time than a week to known about the organism which is not a member of our body and how to fight against them and this interval is sufficient for their developing microbes for causing disease.

This consumed sequencer of inoculation is started in May 1974 by the world health organization to saving the lives of kids in 1988. The adaptation of determination to the universal suppression of polio. This organization is beginning in 1978 with the detached the extermination of polio.

In 2016 seven thousand eight hundred and forty-seven serious drooping paralysis patient are admitted in our nation. While in Punjab region three thousand nine hundred and thirty-nine his is the maximum patient cases are admitting. This is calculated that more than three lakhs kids in age lower than 5 years are spending polio prevalent regions in our nation. Otherwise in our nation polio cases will be a failure but they do not intermittent.

Our country less educated about injection or inoculation and undesirable boldness laterally with holy feature decline polio injection and re-emergence in polio case of our nation display hazard to statement in holy or worldwide equal. Head of the World Health Organization is warned the universal dispersed of rough poliovirus a publicized and community well-being spare of worldwide anxiety. Mass media is variable boldness make responsiveness diminish anxiety or inspire members of polio injection. Board casting media transistor and television help in increased the knowledge in the community, and the existence of an influence instrument and this instrument is helpful the goal anticipated societies. Board casting media show their effect on the polio injection.

The marking point of this investigation is to search the effect of board casting media for conceiving polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0) in families and entirely holy persons of our nation. The purpose is to link polio injection in families who have an experience by the board casting media.

METHODOLOGY:

Our country demographics and well-being study is the third examination showed our country is a region of universal demography and well-being study sequencer. This examination is receiving in completely in parts of Pakistan without Azad Jammu or Kashmir. Federally managed ancestral regions or limited military and saved regions. Survey held at Mayo Hospital, Lahore (January – November 2017). Methodical specimen method is applied or fourteen thousand families six thousand nine hundred and forty-four in city regions or seven thousand and fifty-six in countryside regions are selected. Where in thirteen thousand four hundred and sixty-four engaged families, twelve thousand nine hundred and forty-three families are cross-examined. In chosen families, thirteen thousand five hundred and fifty-eight are marital females or thirteen thousand one hundred and thirty-four are marital males in the age limit of (15 – 49) years are cross-examined. In retort frequency of females is 93% or in males 79%.

Arithmetical correspondences in a societal knowledge variety 21 are utilized in a cross arrangement for verbalizing bench to judge part of electronic board casting to pick the polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0) the entire parts in our nation. The link in both TV or transistor (self-governing changes) or polio injection quantity (needy changes) is checked by SPSS multinomial logistic deterioration investigates. The polio-value is <0.05 is careful statistically important.

RESULTS:

Transistor experience of families or polio injection. Board 1 express picked polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0) I families which have no transistor, and inboard 2 expresses picked polio injection quantity (1, 2, 3, 0) in families which have a transistor experience.

Board 1 or 2 prove that the kids need more polio injection quantity, (1, 2, 3, 0) in these families which having a transistor experience and these kids which are not experienced with a transistor in families. Those family's kids which having transistor take extremely polio injection amount (1, 2, 3, 0) and their information of polio inoculation are present with their parents as compared to those family's kids which do not have a transistor. The dissimilarity of injection quantity time is shown in the report for taking polio injection quantity (2, 3, 0) are extra in families these families which not having a transistor then those which having a transistor. The rural region in Balochistan 76.3% of kids in families is spent their life without transistor and not taking polio 0 amount its shows increasing numbers of this disease in Pakistan

Table – I: Households having no transistor and polio injection in all places of Pakistan.

Polio Dose Record	Polio - I			Polio - II			Polio - III			Polio - 0			
	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	
Islamabad	11.6	35.6	51.3	19.2	34.5	45.2	25.5	31.5	41.5	17.5	38.1	43.6	
Punjab	Urban	5.8	38.9	54.7	10.7	35.6	53.6	15.1	32.4	51.3	20.6	38.2	40.3
	Rural	5.8	28.8	65.8	9.7	25.6	64.6	14.2	22.3	62.4	35.8	26.3	37.1
Sindh	Urban	12.8	31.2	55.8	21.8	27.4	50.5	29.8	23.8	45.8	21.4	32.4	45.6
	Rural	20.9	5.7	73.4	27.5	4.3	68.3	33.4	3.4	63.4	44.8	7.3	47.6
KPK	Urban	13.5	31.3	55.4	16.7	28.5	54.2	22.4	25.2	52.4	21.3	32.4	45
	Rural	26.5	25.6	47.6	32.1	23.4	44.4	36.6	20.2	42.6	39.3	25.7	34.6
Baluchistan	Urban	21.7	9.9	68.2	25.2	8.7	66.2	31.4	7.6	61.4	42.9	11.6	45.5
	Rural	37.6	2.5	64.6	36.1	2.4	61.1	43.2	1.6	54.8	76.4	3.9	19.9
Gilgit Baltistan	12.3	22.6	64.5	17.8	19.8	61.6	24.6	16.4	57.7	54.4	21.9	23.5	

Table – II: Households having transistor and polio injection in all places of Pakistan.

Polio Dose Record	Polio - I			Polio - II			Polio - III			Polio - 0			
	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	
Islamabad	5.8	37.6	55.2	13.2	34.5	50.6	17.5	33.2	47.2	12.4	38.3	47.2	
Punjab	Urban	0.9	39.4	59.7	3.6	36.5	59.7	10.4	31.7	57.8	27.2	35.5	37.5
	Rural	7.3	27.4	65.7	12.3	23.2	64.4	15.6	22.4	62	35.3	27.4	37.3
Sindh	Urban	11.6	26.4	58.5	24.1	20.7	51.6	27.5	19.4	49.5	13.7	27.5	55.3
	Rural	11.4	3.8	84.4	17	3.2	79.9	20.8	3.2	76.5	32.5	4.8	62.8
KPK	Urban	15.4	28.6	55.5	18.4	27.3	54.2	29.4	24.3	46.5	21.1	30.5	47.2
	Rural	28.5	22.6	48.7	31.4	21.9	46.8	35.7	19.5	45.1	34.2	25.5	40.4
Baluchistan	Urban	24.8	15.5	59.6	28.3	13.9	56.6	35.7	9.8	49.9	45.5	16.7	38.2
	Rural	34	4.3	61.3	38.4	3.4	57.6	44.8	2.9	51.6	62.4	3.6	34
Gilgit Baltistan	18.9	17.9	63.6	23.8	16.1	60.2	33.5	13.5	52.9	66.4	18.2	15.9	

TV experience in families or they influence in picking polio injection quantity. Board 3 of polio injection amount picked in families in which do not have TV and in board 4 about of these which have a TV in their families.

The boards show these kids from families which have a TV and take an obviously extra polio injection amount (1, 2, 3, 0), extra injection timing on the report and inoculated description important extra in parents in the kids of these families which do not have a TV. The countryside regions in Balochistan, 80.6% kids of families which do not have a television and polio 0 amount do not give to the kids and it shows the top frequency in our nation.

Table I or II expressions statistical important or link in between television and transistor with polio injection amount (1, 2, 3, 0).

Table – III: Families having no television and polio injection in all parts of our nation.

Polio Dose Record		Polio - I			Polio - II			Polio - III			Polio - 0		
		No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)
Islamabad		22.2	36.6	38.4	29.9	37.4	31.8	37.4	35.7	26.1	24.7	38.2	34.4
Punjab	Urban	3.4	33.3	63.3	6.8	31.8	61.2	11.2	30.5	58.4	26.5	32.5	41.1
	Rural	5.5	24.6	69.8	10.2	20.6	68.9	13.5	18.6	67.4	38.8	22	38.5
Sindh	Urban	17.8	15.6	66.3	29.2	13.9	57.1	37.2	8.7	53.5	29.7	17.8	52.4
	Rural	24.5	3.1	72.4	30	1.5	68.2	36.2	1.1	62.6	51.5	4.5	43.4
KPK	Urban	21.2	28.1	50.7	25.1	24.5	50.5	30.8	20.6	48.3	30.4	29.6	38
	Rural	31.2	21.5	47.4	35.6	19.8	44.5	40	16.8	42.4	46.6	21.4	31.7
Baluchistan	Urban	38.8	3.5	57.6	39.8	3.5	57.1	46.4	1.4	52.4	69.2	3.4	27.4
	Rural	37.4	2.1	60.5	41.6	1.8	56.3	49.7	1.5	48.8	80.6	3.1	16.4
Gilgit Baltistan		19.4	16.2	64.4	25.4	14.1	60.3	33.4	11.5	54.1	69.2	16.2	14.8

Table – IV: Families having television and polio injection in all parts of our nation.

Polio Dose Record	Polio - I			Polio - II			Polio - III			Polio - 0			
	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	No	Yes (Date on Card)	Yes (Reported by Parents)	
Islamabad	8.2	35.4	54.9	15.8	34.2	48.8	21.6	31.3	45.6	14.7	38.2	46.3	
Punjab	Urban	5.6	39.7	54.2	10.4	36.3	53.2	15.4	32.8	51.4	20.6	38.5	39.8
	Rural	6.7	32.4	61.3	9.6	29.3	60.8	14.8	26.4	15.8	33.6	29.6	35.9
Sindh	Urban	11.6	33.2	54.6	20.8	29.1	49.6	28.4	25.6	45.1	19.5	34.2	45.5
	Rural	11.8	9.9	78.2	20	8.2	71.7	25.2	6.8	67.7	30.3	10.2	58.5
KPK	Urban	10.3	32.3	57.4	13.4	30.4	56.3	20.6	26.8	52.3	16.7	33.6	49.2
	Rural	18.6	32.4	49.2	24.7	29.3	45.7	29.5	25.8	43.6	23.3	34.2	42.6
Baluchistan	Urban	19.3	13.8	66.6	23.4	12.3	64.2	29.5	9.9	58.4	37.9	15.7	46.5
	Rural	26.5	4.6	68.3	29.6	3.6	65.4	34.4	2.8	61.8	58.5	4.7	36
Gilgit Baltistan	9.7	26.1	64.1	14.5	23.1	62.3	22	19.4	57.8	47.5	25.1	27.1	

These board evidently prove there is a very important link is present in between transistor and TV with polio injection amount (1, 2, 3, 0). SPSS multinomial logistic deterioration perfect is utilized for this purpose.

Table – V: Families having a transistor with polio injection amount

Polio Dose	Injected Amount
Dose Zero	599.487
Dose One	390.226
Dose Two	313.793
Dose Three	280.772

DISCUSSION:

The experiment proves the electronic board casting (transistor and television) experience in families and shows influence in polio injection and proved that kids gave extra polio injection amount in families which do not have a transistor and TV. Kids of these families which have a television have noticeable and extra polio injection amount (1, 2, 3, 0), injection noticeable in report and injection described by parents as compared to those kids of families which do not have a television. Transistor or television are statistically important or link with polio injection amount (1, 2, 3, 0).

Where present conditional of 6th community and families survey 2018 prove that our country community is 207,774,520 and yearly development frequency is (1998-2017) are twenty percent. Rendering of a World Bank approximation, the community shall in beneath 234,377,000 in 2027 or thirty-two percent community members shall in beneath fourteen years old. Community beneath five years old in our country want extraordinary responsiveness and methods of polio injection.

PDHS 2012-13 supposed the fare increase in the counting of kids in our country these kids which are

not inoculated by polio injection and then they facing polio disease. Lack of education about polio injection and variety of obstacle has present in kid's healthiness and palisade or their requirement to get meet all these kids of polio injection complete extraordinary superiority vaccination happenings. It is easy for the country operation to practice of electronic board casting (transistor or television) to protected kids from polio.

PDHS 2012-13 nearly regions which are not sheltered or collection remain incomplete impartial for safety motives. Its prove that polio injection members do not extend some regions of our country which included Baluchistan, for the main portion of regional or federal administration, and the law of enforcement is maintained by organizations, is required. Main policies or struggles is essential for this regions to maintain and protect from scattering of world poliovirus. Danger investigation fine succeeded polio injection strategies and high population should be serving to protect kids from poliovirus.

In our country city regions community, only 38.8 and in outside country regions is 61.2% of the total community for this reason outside country regions is

more needed to responsiveness for polio injection. Transistor is more needed in outside country regions because these people listening to transistor channels and daily update when they have a relaxation time and also in their functioning field. Mass board casting play a basic role in telecasting the news and important facts reach to the all people through this mass board casting.

The experiment effects prove that in outside country regions in Pakistan also taking the transistor but extremely kids are unvaccinated as compare to the city kids in which large numbers of kids are vaccinated. Baluchistan outside regions families which not having television and transistor also having an extreme number of unvaccinated kids. The transistor in outside country regions is basic data reason, also significant and should be important for altering, performance and their thinking judgment leaders or parents move towards the polio injection. This investigation proves that polio injection does not take to the entire kids of Pakistan. It is very important that family should be having knowledge about polio injection. The outside region of our country just because of less knowledge about polio injection as compared to the city people because of electronic board casting. The electronic board casting (transistor or television) act as the main instrument in reducing vaccination differences too actual utilization or it eliminates obstacle will be caring for the regulator of polio and also their injections.

The investigation proves that contact in families evidently proliferation in kids. They make a wisdom of duty to taken polio injection dose and make a mark on the in the polio injection report. If graphic descriptions effect fitness performance that proliferation education and alter the performance so that is reason television is main in polio injection attentiveness since television fights are charge actual that of huge community-based interferences and programmed to educate or make responsiveness between different societies. Fitness economical had hinge part to protect members survives. The amount of spending OF fitness budget the GDP (2014) In Bangladesh is 2.8%, Bhutan expended 3.6%, Sri Lanka assigned 3.6%, Nepal has 5.8%, and the Maldives recycled up to 13.7%, and in last Pakistan paradoxically merely expended 2.6%. Here remains extra essential to proliferation health costs budget, then fitness section should capable for track polio injection responsiveness planned in electronic board casting. Kids injection planned is extremely helpful or had a large period helpful for kids and injection also for saving them in a lifetime from injection preventable disorder.

The investigation proves that polio injection (polio 1,2,3,0) kids have extreme in families which have a television and transistor as for extreme polio injection attention here are essential of exact calculated in dissimilar stages, for production of essential dishonorable to screen, monitoring of unvaccinated kids, its only produced public created knowledge planned done acoustic or cinematic evidence and communications.

Its experiments proved that electronic board casting visible had influence in extreme of polio injection, by means of this injection attention will be extreme to help in the creation of polio permitted nation. The survey of Pakistan only shows an electronic board casting influences in polio injections. They show if more community has a very little amount of polio knowledge close here is taken correct data about injection, they boosted 39% of injection amount in kids.

Electronic board casting (transistor or television) very suggestively progress of polio injection attention of Pakistan. They desire extreme level superiority transistor or television ads the correct period of making responsiveness about polio, refining education about this disorder property declining distress or knowledge in a population of polio injection.

CONCLUSION:

Electronic boards casting television or transistor, play a significant character in polio injection also show energetic in polio extermination of our country. Correct scheming or transferring of influential board casting communications in the main period for making responsiveness about polio alteration performance or boldness of polio injection.

REFERENCES:

1. Pakistan Bureau of Statistics. The government of Pakistan. Provisional summary results of sixth population and housing census-2017. <http://www.pbscensus.gov.pk/>
2. The World Bank. Health, Nutrition and Population. Pakistan, 2027. Available from:<http://datatopics.worldbank.org/health/population> [accessed on 1 June 2017].
3. Morales M, Tangermann RH, Wassilak SG. Progress toward Polio Eradication - Worldwide, 2015-2016. *MMWR Morbi Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2016; 65(18):470-3.
4. Elhamidi y, Mahamud A, Safdar M, Al Tamimi W, Jorba J, Mbaeyi C, et al. Progress Toward Poliomyelitis Eradication — Pakistan, January

- 2016–September 2017. *Morbi Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2017 Nov; 66(46):1276-1280.
5. Farag NH, Alexander J, Hadler S, Quddus A, Durry E, Wadood MZ, et al Progress toward poliomyelitis eradication--Afghanistan and Pakistan, January 2013–August 2014. *Morbi Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2014 Oct; 63(43):973-7.
 6. Gardner TJ, Diop OM, Jorba J, Chavan S, Ahmed J, Anand A. Surveillance to Track Progress Toward Polio Eradication — Worldwide, 2016–2017. *Morbi Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2018; 67(14):418–423.
 7. Khan MU, Ahmad A, Aqeel T, Salman S, Ibrahim Q, Idrees J. et al. Knowledge, attitudes and perceptions towards polio immunization among residents of two highly affected regions of Pakistan. *BMC Public Health.* 2015; 15:1100
 8. Owais A, Hanif B, Siddiqui AR, Agha A, Zaidi AK, Does improving maternal knowledge of vaccines impact infant immunization rates? A community-based randomized-controlled trial in Karachi, Pakistan. *BMC Public Health.* 2011:239
 9. Sheikh A, Iqbal B. Reasons for non-vaccination in pediatric patients visiting tertiary care centers in a polio-prone country. *Arch Public Health.* 2013 Jul; 71(1):19.
 10. Fatima K, Qadri I. Battle against poliovirus in Pakistan. *J Infect Dev Ctries.* 2013; 7(11):897-9.
 11. Glik DC, Massey PM, Gipson J, Dieng T, Preliip M, Rideau A. Health-related media use among youth audiences in Senegal. *Health Promote Int.* 2016 Mar; 31(1):73-82.
 12. Racicot-Matta C, Wilcke M, England GM. Development of radio dramas for health communication pilot intervention in Canadian Inuit communities *Health Promote Int.* 2016 ;31(1):175-86.
 13. Kim M, Yoo BK. Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of a Television Campaign to Promote Seasonal Influenza Vaccination among the Elderly. *Value Health.* 2015; 18 (5):622-30.
 14. WHO. Pakistan. Statistics. <http://www.who.int/countries/pak/en>
 15. Anekwe TD, Kumar S. The effect of a vaccination program on child anthropometry: evidence from India's Universal Immunization Program. *J Public Health (Oxf).* 2012 ; 34(4):489-97.
 16. Owais A, Khowaja AR, Ali SA, Zaidi AK. Pakistan has expanded programmer on immunization: an overview in the context of polio eradication and strategies for improving coverage. *Vaccine.* 2013; 31(33):3313-9.
 17. Bosch X, Banerjee K, Burton A. Unvaccinated

children in years of increasing coverage: how many and who are they? Evidence from 96 low- and middle-income countries. *Trop Med Int Health.* 2012; 17 (6):697-710.